

Assessing the Impact of Electronic Information Resources on Performance in Basic Science and Technology among Secondary School Students in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study is an assessment of electronic information resources on performance in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Katsina State. 3 objectives and corresponding research questions and hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and t-test to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consists of 618 (318 Male and 300 female) junior secondary school class three (JSSIII) students in Katsina Zonal Education Board during the 2022/2023 academic session. 253 (153 Male and 100 Female) Students constitutes the sample size of the study. Hence this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire rated on five scale Linkert. The result showed that, there is significant relation between the use of electronic information resources and performance in basic science among secondary school students in Katsina state. The study concluded that, electronic information resources in the yield positive outcome as it gives the students the opportunity to use independent learning and increase the performance in basic science. Based on this the study recommend that the government should provide and deploy adequate electronic information resources in Junior Secondary schools for effective teaching and learning of Basic Science

Keyword: Electronic Information Resources, performance, Basic Science and Technology

Introduction

Education is considered as the overall development of an individual, physically, mentally, morally, socially and economically while teaching and learning in any level of education can only be effective and efficient when adequate provision of educational infrastructure and physical facilities are made. Especially in public schools where there is increase in population. Basic science and Technology are a core subject at the junior secondary level of education (Sadi & Haruna, 2020) as specified in the National Policy on Education (2004). It is an introductory science course and a necessary background to all scientific and engineering careers. Basic science is described as a branch of knowledge that expresses the central idea of scientific integration via the use of ideas and principles. Teaching and learning of Basic science and technology has increasingly been taking advantage of electronic information resources managed by librarians, instructors or publishers. These tools are varied and may include websites, social media such as Face-book, Twitter and YouTube and communication media such as email, chat rooms, instant messaging systems, and web conferencing systems like Big Blue Button and Adobe Connect. The transition of all forms of intellectual potentials to digital, the process of digitizing printed materials, including scientific works, educational and methodological materials, periodicals and much more, becomes the most important incentive to change the format of Secondary Education in Nigeria (Ferreira, Paterson, and Hakone, 2018). (Alhabeeb, and Rowley, 2018). That is why Nigeria's basic science curriculum requires students to engage in any activities that encourage critical thinking. This is evident in the objectives of basic science curriculum (NERDC, 2004) which include to enable students to:

1. Develop interest in science and technology: with deployment of electronic information resources in teaching and learning basic science and technology the interest of students at junior secondary school level can be arose to achieve this objective
2. Acquire basic knowledge and skills in science and technology: Electronic information resources that has voice, audio, data videos is regarded as a critical tool for preparing and educating students with the required skills for the global work place

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3. Use your talents, technical knowledge, and abilities to satisfy society needs: electronic information resources can be used to achieved this objective. By using electronic information resources it will help, support, enhances students and complement existing classroom traditional practices.
4. Develop the skills necessary to pursue a career in science or technology: using electronic information resources by students at Junior secondary school level is a great opportunity for promoting students' intellectual qualities through higher order thinking, problem solving, improved communication skills and deep understanding of the learning tools and concepts to be taught necessary to pursue a career in science or technology
5. Prepare yourself for more science and technology studies: Electronic information resources plays a major role in human activities in everyday living in order to cope and adopt to the demand of the environment. With this objective it is generally agreed that students can be prepared for more science and technology studies by using electronic information resources.

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, the use of modern ICT facilities such as electronic information resources become imperative in the sense that they reduce obstruction, and capture students' attention and interests, promotes students' active preparation and improve students' ability to search learning concepts. The uses of electronic information resources according to Burk, Lyons, Noriega and Polovina (2013) are manifold and include:

1. The dissemination of common material such as course outlines, lecture notes and grades: This can be seen in the use of electronic information resources by students at secondary school level as it holds out the opportunity to revolutionaries' pedagogical methods, expand access to quality education and improve the management of education in providing material such as course outlines, lecture notes and grades and allowing students to receive primary and supplementary lecture and course materials
2. Allowing students to solve homework-type material at their own pace and receive personalized feedback: there is no doubt that, it is quite over wheeling to stress that electronic information resources simplify methods and strategies of acquisition of knowledge there by allowing students to solve problem at their own pace.
3. Rapidly fixing errors in previous communications or misconceptions about particular course material: The use of electronic information resources at junior secondary school does not only prepare students for the information age and globalization, it helps the students in fixing errors or misconceptions about particular topic under basic science and technology.
4. Coordinating the activities of the instructors, teaching assistants, laboratory coordinators and students everybody gets the same message at the same time: electronic information resources that that are connected via internet proto cold (IP) and non-IP network can be used by the instructors, teaching or laboratory technicians and students there by allowing everybody to gets the same message at the same time

Universal Service Provisional fund in its objective to promote seamless aces to online and off-line remote educational resources and adoption of smart education to increase ICT literacy among teachers and studentsl in collaboration with Nigeria Communication Commissions (NCC) built Students Knowledge Center in up to 369 public Secondary schools across the country, with the centers Equipped with computers and free internet for students to access resources on-line, but the centres are not duly put into use. The federal Ministry of Educations also partner with an Edtech private company (Skool Media) which is to provide: students' Experience Centers that will be fully equipped with Laptops and Internet to enhance Students' Research, teachers' Experience Center equip with laptops and internet for teachers to update themselves, prepare for Exams and get information on the internet and to digitalize classrooms by installing Projectors and each classes having its separate Laptop in them so that lessons can be delivered digitally.

In supplement of the above assertions, Xiao and Hu (2019), Adekunle, and Opeyemi, (2021) opined that use of electronic information resources improves the reading performance of students, especially those from a disadvantaged socio-economic background. The researchers observed that the impact of electronic information resources on students' reading performance gap caused by their socio-economic status changed from negative to positive. they consider that a more interactive and attractive digital environment, as well as the use of creative activities in teaching practices with ICT devices, could explain this positive effect of electronic information resources on reading performance among students from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds. Governments' attention has over the years been drawn to the issues of quality of education in Katsina state and the relevance of the curriculum to the needs of the society. So far, it has been noted that a giant stride has been made towards improving the quality of teachers, instructional resources and facilities to enhance learning. However, in spite of government efforts, there are still notable challenges in relation the adoption of ICT facilities in teaching and learning process, the challenges lie in giving out information, directives and timely release of funds in addition to low ICT capacity of the personnel. Based on these reasons the researchers were motivated to embark on a study to assess electronic information resources on performance in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Katsina State

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Electronic Information resources (EIR), which include a whole range of educational materials, allow varying the forms of teaching and contribute to improving the quality of education. Omoike (2013) pointed out that electronic information resources comprise instructional materials such as audio and video cassettes, CD-ROM, television and radio broadcast as well as multimedia components such as computer and satellites. Titilope, Abobi; and Olayemi, (2022) defined Electronic resources as those materials that require computer access, whether through a personal computer, mainframe, or hand-held mobile device. It is the collective means of communication by which general public or populace is kept informed about the day-to-day happenings in the society.

Academic Performance is one of the most widely used variables to try to understand how information and communication technologies affect student learning outcomes. thus, academic performance may be difficult to measure, it is however seen in the grades obtained by students. Several authors agree that academic performance is the result of learning, prompted by the teaching activity by the teacher and produced by the student. Performance. Giunchiglia, Fausto, Zeni, Mattia, Gobbi, Elisa, Bignotti, Enrico, Bison, Ivano, (2018) defined academic performance as a standard for assessing a student learning status and usually measured with two dimensions, namely GPA (Grade Point Average) and CFU Credito Formativo University

This section reviewed some of the related literature conducted by different scholars on the impact of electronic information and academic performance and the study also reveal and accepted that electronic information sources have an impact on their work. Olajide Olabode (2016) explore the impact of usage of e-resources on the academic performance of the undergraduates of Federal University Oye-Ekiti, (FUOYE), Nigeria. This research is a survey. The population for this study includes the final year students of faculties of Social Science, Humanities and Science, Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria, of the 2015/2016 academic session. 150 students were chosen by simple random sampling. The data collected were analyzed quantitatively with the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Figures and tables were used to present the results of the findings. From the total of 150 copies of questionnaires distributed, 144 copies, representing 96%, were filled and returned. Results indicated that use of electronic resources had a positive impact on students' academic performance. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that more emphasis should be laid on the acquisition of electronic resources so as to give room for wider and multiple access to information resources in order to meet the information needs of diverse users

Bakare, and Solomon (2022) investigated the relevance of Internet resources on the academic performance of secondary school students in Esan West LGA of Edo State of Nigeria. The questionnaire was the instrument; 500 copies were administered, 425 were retrieved and analysed. The descriptive survey research method was adopted. Findings show that students have access to the Internet. Students access the Internet to keep in touch with friend, get current information, improve their reading habits, and be exposed to global issues; the mostly used Internet resources are social media, Search Engines and Electronic Newspapers. The challenges to access to the Internet are cost and speed, lack of proper training/guidance on how to use the Internet. The use of Internet resources has improved their performance during test and examination. Nonetheless, the use of Internet resources have not helped them to learn self-study skills, develop information seeking skills, nor develop life-long learning skills The research recommends that students should be properly trained and constantly guided on the profitable use of the Internet and its resources for their academic pursuits; also mobile telecommunication companies should make Internet access cheaper, as well as faster so that students can access the Internet for their academic works.

Junfeng Li (2022). conducted a study aimed to explore the impact of the usage of electronic devices on students' academic performance using Ordinal Logistic Regression. Through the data analysis of the CFPS database, design electronic device usage, key school, perception of Internet as in dependent variables, and the academic performance is used as a dependent variable as a Ordinal Logistic model. The findings revealed that the length of the use of electronic devices has a significant negative correlation with the academic performance of students. Whether students belong to key schools and students' perception of the importance of the Internet to learning have no significant effect on academic performance. The results show that academic performance can be improved by controlling the length of time students use electronic devices

Several international studies have shown little improvement in performance attributed to the use of Electronic Information Resources, although other reviews have shown positive results in relation to certain curricular areas. In a study conducted by Mullis, (2017) it was revealing that students in schools that do not utilise electronic information resources performed lower than students in schools that utilised electronic information resources, although this correlation is difficult to interpret, since socio-economic levels and teaching methodologies are highly interrelated. Despite the increase and widespread use of electronic information resources among junior secondary school students, there are still challenges that are significantly preventing the effective access and usage of electronic information resources in secondary schools. According to Sife (2016), the challenges facing students could be lack or inadequate ICTs infrastructure in secondary schools, lack of awareness among

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the students, limited power supply, low bandwidth as well as lack or inadequate budget for adoption of technologies in secondary schools.

In a preliminary survey conducted it was found that, these challenges might be caused by lack of support from the parents, government, education managers, parents and even the students themselves. It is therefore based on these assertions the research was conducted to assess electronic information resources on performance in Basic Science and Technology among secondary school students in Katsina State

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this study are:

1. To assess electronic information resource available for teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology among Junior Secondary School Students in Katsina State
2. To examine performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State
3. To examine performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state

Research Questions:

1. What type of electronic information resource are available for teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology among Junior Secondary School Students in Katsina State?
2. What is the level performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?
3. Is there any difference in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated tested at 0.5 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. the population of the study consists of 618 (318 Male and 300 female) junior secondary school class three (JSSIII) students in Katsina Zonal Education Board during the 2022/2023 academic session. 253 (153 Male and 100 Female) Students constitutes the sample size of the study. Hence this was arrived at using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire rated on five scale likert. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistic while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.005 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What type of electronic information resource are available for teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology among Junior Secondary School Students in Katsina State?

Table 1. Available type of electronic information resources

S/N	Type of Electronic information resources	SA	A	SD	D	Decision
1	E-journals	38 (15.1%)	23 (9.1%)	129 (50.9%)	63 (24.9%)	Not available
2	E-newspapers	31 (12.3%)	43 (16.9%)	137 (54.2%)	42 (16.6%)	Available
3	E-magazines	109	74	22	40	Available

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4	E-research reports	(43.1%) 23	(29.3%) 10	(8.6%) 186	(15.8%) 34	Not available
5	Card readers (e-readers)	(9.0%) 119	(3.9%) 73	(73.5%) 38	(13.5%) 23	Available
6	E-graphics board	(47.1%) 157	(28.8%) 42	(15.1%) 21	(9.1%) 33	Not available
7	Multimedia (MM) Projector	(62.1%) 119	16.6% 73	(8.3%) 38	(13.1%) 23	Available
8	Computer	(47.1%) 157	(28.8%) 22	(15.1%) 41	(9.1%) 33	Available
9	Flash memories	(62.0%) 102	(8.6%) 71	(62.2%) 29	(13.0%) 42	Available
10	E- Library	(40.31%) 156	(29.3%) 34	(8.6%) 23	(16.6%) 40	Available
		(61.6%)	(13.5%)	(9.0%)	(15.8%)	

Table above present data on available type of Electronic information resources in Junior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education board. The table shows the percentage scores of the response of the types of electronic information resources available for students. From the above table, items 3,5,9,8,10, are available, while items 1,2,4,6, are not available.

Research Question 2

What is the level performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?

Table 1. Level of performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device

S/N	level of performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device	SA	A	SD	D	Decision
1	The performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is high	157 (62.1)	42 16.6)	21 (8.3)	33 (13.1)	Positive
2	The performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is low	23 (9.1)	38 (15.1)	73 (28.8)	119 (47.1)	Negative

Table 2 above present data on level of performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those expose to lecture teaching method in Katsina State. The result shows that the performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is high.

Research Question 3

Is there any difference in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state?

Table 3: Differences in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state

S/N	Differences in the performance of male and female students	SA	A	SD	D	Decision
1	Male students perform better that female counter part when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device	58 (22.9)	30 (11.8)	100 (39.5)	57 (22.5)	Negative

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3	Female students perform better than male counterparts when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device	100 (39.5)	57 (22.5)	58 (22.9)	30 (11.8)	Positive
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Table above presents data on differences in the performance of male and female students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device in Katsina state. The result shows that female students perform better than male counterparts when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device based on the percentage scores of the response.

Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Table 4: t-test showing difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State

	x	n	S ²	df	T-cal	T-crit	decision
Electronic information resources	2.58	86					
Students Academic Performance	2.96	169	0.38	253	1.12	1.96	Accepted

Significant at $p < 0.05$, of 2.53 critical = 1.96

Data in Table I indicates that the calculated t-test is 1.12 while the critical t-value is 1.96 at .05 level of significance. This implies that the calculated value is less than the critical value. The null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, there is a significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Table 5: t-test showing difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State

	x	n	S ²	df	T-cal	T-crit	decision
Electronic Information resources	3.85	98					
Female students' Academic Performance	2.34	157	0.62	253	3.51	1.96	Rejected

Significant at $p < 0.05$, $df = 2.53$ critical value = + 1.96

Table 2 revealed that the calculated t-test 3.51 is greater than the table value 1.98 at .05 level of confidence. The null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis which holds that there is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State in Katsina Zonal Education board is thereby upheld.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the result presented it showed that, E-Magazines, Card readers (e-readers), Multimedia (MM) Projector, computer, Flash memories and E-Library are among the available types of electronic information resources in secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality assurance. This corroborates with the finding of Ternenge, Tofi Simon and Kashimana, Fanafa, (2019) concluded in his study that e-journals, e-newspapers, on-line public access catalogue (OPAC), CD-Rom database, e-magazines, e-books, on-line database, e-research reports, virtual library on-line, science direct online and Ebscohost reference databases are not available in most of the secondary schools in Nigeria they were found only in higher institutions. Similarly in a study conducted by Adekunle, and Opeyemi, (2021) indicated that the most used E-learning platform really helped the students during the as it kept them busy and able to make good use of the long break and exposed them to the use of digital devices for Learning,

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Based on the result presented it was revealed that, the performance of students taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device is high and female students perform better than male counterpart when taught Basic science and technology using electronic information device. This is in-line with the finding of Hu (2018) in his study he found that students in countries with higher overall levels of digital competences were more likely to achieve better academic results. Finally, the results indicated that there is no significant difference between use of electronic information resources on female students' academic performance of Junior Secondary Schools.

Conclusion

Based on the research conducted on in this study, it showed that electronic information resources give the students opportunity to use independent learning and increase performance in basic science, while retaining semantic competencies reading, reading habits and the ability to analyse textual material. It was concluded that, there is significant relation between the use of electronic information resources and students' academic performance of Junior Secondary Schools while there is no significant difference between use of electronic information resources on female students' academic performance of Junior Secondary Schools.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on findings:

1. The government should provide and deploy adequate electronic information resources in Junior Secondary schools for effective teaching and learning of Basic Science.
2. The government should embark on orientation, training and retraining of both students and teachers on how to search and use electronic information resources in the secondary schools
3. Government should make emphasis in the budget formulation to consider electronic information resources as the important educational Infrastructural facilities that should be provided in the schools for effective teaching
4. There is need for school administrators to report any damage and problem to the technicians for repair and maintenance of electronic information resources being used in in the schools.

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